

RESPONSE PAPER 1**LAST NAME: NCUBE****FIRST NAME: SIBUSIWE****PROGRAM CODE : DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

This response paper will give an overview of the key concepts learnt in this course based on the course pack revised by Prof Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr Kabiru Gulma, First, I will highlight what I understood to be the most important aspects of good academic writing, then I will proceed to give my own reactions to the course content. Finally, I will write a conclusion emphasising what I found most beneficial and how I will apply the concepts in my studies and work.

There are several key concepts that make up good academic writing. The course pack divided these into chapters which include, essay writing, how to research the topic, “researching provides the knowledge and evidence that allows you to develop a thesis and argument to answer the essay question (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 2), organising your ideas and the steps involved in writing the essay. An important aspect of essay writing is ensuring that you reference the sources of your material and of course editing until you are satisfied that the essay is well-written. A good essay “aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 1). An academically sound essay will require investment in time, as such, the authors advise that students give themselves adequate time to plan, research, organise and finally write the essay. Once written, the student will need to review the essay a number of times to ensure it meets the expected standard and that it adequately addressed the question. The essay must have an introduction, a body and a conclusion.

Care must be taken in researching and writing the essay that the student acknowledges the sources of information through the use of citations. These may be in the form of quotes or paraphrase. Students must avoid committing the academic offense of plagiarism. Cleenewerck and Gulma define plagiarism as “taking someone else’s words

or ideas... and not giving credit to the author” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 5). It could also involve presenting someone else’s work as your own. In both instances, the consequences may be grave. It is therefore essential that credit is given to the originators of the concept or idea that is included in the essay. This is called referencing.

In order to write well, the writer must observe a number of rules such as ensuring that the language used is consistent, and that correct grammar has been used. Of note is the importance of using the appropriate writing style. A number of style guides are available and these help the writer to conform to expected standards by institutions and publishing houses in particular. It is important therefore for the writer to know which style to use at any given time.

2) ESSENTIAL ELEMENTS OF A GOOD ESSAY

I found the course material very useful in outlining what constitutes a well-written essay. I was intrigued by the level of detail that as a writer I must have. Starting with the very simple building blocks of essay writing. As the authors stated, “essay writing is not a linear process” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 1). I found the tips given in the course material simple yet very useful. I have started utilising the recommended steps as I write reports in my day-to-day work with positive results. A point that resonated well with me is the importance of starting early and how that can be invaluable in giving myself time to not only do the research but to edit the essay as well. Now, as I edit some of the reports and articles that I often write, the quality has improved significantly. I am able to refine the language resulting in a final draft that is a markedly improved version of the first.

Another salient point in the lesson material which I often use with good success in my work is that of having a colleague review most of what I write. I have found that having another eye review my work only makes for a stronger final product. Yet another benefit in my view, is that the colleague will often be able to easily spot any biases, repetition and glaring gaps.

In order to be an effective writer, the course material outlines a number of important considerations. I will highlight the ones that I particularly resonated with or found challenging.

a) Plagiarism

I strongly agree with the instructors that plagiarism is an unacceptable practice. I particularly liked the two types of plagiarism that the material alluded to. The first, and in my view the most offensive, is that of getting someone else to write documents or assignments for another and this person then handing them in as his or her work. Sadly, this practise is becoming increasingly prevalent in some of the organisations I have worked with. The second form of plagiarism mentioned in the course pack is that of me using another’s work without “giving credit to the author” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 5).

Not only is plagiarism unethical it is unfair on the originator of the ideas. I have been in situations where a superior will take a report that I have written or concepts I have shared with him or her and then submit them to a higher authority as his or her own.

An area where plagiarism is often demonstrated is in the online space and social media. I have often seen many individuals share a quote on their status or tweets without referencing the writer. In my view, there should be some kind of consequence for such behaviour in those spaces too. Thankfully now, YouTube and Facebook have become strict about copyright infringements and hopefully this will extend to plagiarism.

b) The use of English

When I read through this section of the course pack, I was amazed at just how much there is to consider when using American or British Standard English beyond the spellings. I was not much aware of the differences in punctuation that must be observed too.

I appreciated the explanation given on the wide usage of American English based on America's influence in global politics, trade, and commerce; the larger population size in America compared to the UK and influence of American media globally among others (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 27). Incidentally, I was reviewing an inception report written by a colleague this morning and immediately put into use some of the concepts discussed in this section of the course. I saw how easy it is to make basic mistakes in both grammar and punctuations as well as word meanings.

As I reviewed the inception report, I was reminded of the tips given in the video to use spellcheck to help ensure consistency in the type of English used and to be clear from the onset which English I will use. The one tip that stuck in my mind is to make use of the dictionary whenever I am in doubt. Of course, the course material does advise that I can use Grammarly. My only challenge with relying on Grammarly is that I may not end up internalising the principles knowing I can simply press a button and have the computer attend to my mistakes. I am very old school in that regard.

c) Compound words

If there is an aspect of writing that is often confusing, it is knowing which words are compound and which are not. I found the guidance in the course pack beneficial. Again, I am already applying the principles in my writing. What stood out the most was the advice to consult a dictionary when in doubt. I appreciated the distinction between full-time compound words which must always be hyphenated and conditional compound words. These must be "hyphenated as adjectives but not when used as nouns" (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 46). This is a section of the lesson I will re-visit regularly to ensure I internalise the concepts as explained.

d) Style guides

This section was completely new to me. I was not aware of the existence of style guides let alone their usefulness to writers and publishers alike. The authors define a style guide in this manner “a style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021,24). In writing this response paper, I have seen the benefits of using the Turabian style and how easy it is to reference and format the document. The lesson is correct in the view that most writers assume that they have what it takes to write well yet most would benefit from using these acceptable international standards. In my view, style should also be informed by the target audience for my writing. Often times we tend to write big words thinking we are impressing when actually it is off-putting to readers. I agree with keeping language and sentences simple. I have found in my own experience that I enjoy reading authors whose style is simple and user-friendly to me as a reader. As I learnt in the lesson “Writing philosophy does not require elaborate formulations, esoteric words, neologisms and polysyllabophilia” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 15).

By the same token, the writer must avoid monotony and dullness in the text through the use of “stylistic variety”(Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 15). This includes using different words to start sentences and paragraphs as well as using active verbs and voice. All this is necessary to keep the reader engaged and interested to read further.

3) CONCLUSION

Initially when I read that academic writing was the first course on my programme, I asked myself why? Now that I have completed this first period, it makes perfect sense. I am sure that as I progress on the course, I will realise full benefit from it. The content was presented in very simple terms and I appreciate that greatly. However, I still find the grammar aspect rather tedious and at times confusing. In my view, it is taking me back to high school. Thankfully however, I can immediately start implementing the lessons in my day-to-day work. The most important lesson for me is that good writing does not happen by accident, even gifted writers would do well to learn the art and science of good writing. This is what this first lesson was all about.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 3rd ed. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

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